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Abstract:

It is well known that the arts suffer from marginalisation in schools throughout the world. That we privilege literacy and numeracy over the arts is testament to the fact we place greater value on the former as the pinnacle of what counts as knowledge. The arts are squeezed into the margins of a jam-packed curriculum, making it apparent what is highly esteemed and what is considered superfluous. It is tempting to lapse into a debate on the relative merits of the disciplines, but this is invariably counterproductive. Literacy and numeracy are high-stakes in the world and we do our students a disservice if we do not grow their capabilities in these areas. However, we also do them an immense disservice if we ignore their creative, imaginative and artistic abilities. Picasso claimed that children are born artists but we educate them out of it (Robinson, 2007). In addition, Wright (2010) argues: The schooling process often is at odds with young children's imaginative and creative dispositions. It is biased toward teaching children the rule-bound structured symbol systems, where written letters, words and numbers are seen as a 'higher status' mode of representation over self-derived, visual thinking and reflection.

Introduction:

The arts are often considered an indulgence, a frill, an expendable extra. Yet a school that does not have a vibrant arts programme cannot claim it is educating the whole child, nor can it claim that it values what children bring to school. It is curious that the arts are so often sacrificed for subjects deemed more important and more worthy of large chunks of the school timetable. There are two major problems with this.

First, there is much evidence to show that the arts do enhance learning in other areas of the curriculum, especially for students whose strengths lie in bodily, kinaesthetic, visual, haptic, and aural ways of knowing. Using these modes to access learning can enable students who do not usually perform well in literacy and numeracy, for example, to succeed in surprising and sustained ways (e.g., Catterall & Waldorf, 1999; Ewing, 2009; Gibson & Ewing, 2011). The arts are not the cause of alleged issues with achievement in numeracy and literacy, yet for some reason they are the sacrificial lamb. Bolstad's (2011) review of the literature found that the arts contribute to a range of goals, such as fostering creativity and innovation, and developing a sustainable knowledge economy. She also refers to a few large studies that state that students do better overall in schools with rich arts programmes, than those in schools with poor ones.

Secondly, the arts have immense innate value and teach us things that cannot be experienced through other disciplines. Elliot Eisner (2000) elegantly captures the ways in which the arts educate and enhance who we are in his Ten Lessons which are summarised here:

- The arts teach children to make good judgments about qualitative relationships.
- The arts teach children that problems can have more than one solution and that questions can have more than one answer.
- The arts celebrate multiple perspectives.
- The arts teach that purposes in complex forms of problem solving are seldom fixed, but change with circumstance and opportunity.
- The arts make vivid the fact that neither words in their literal form nor number exhaust what we can know.
- The arts teach students that small difference can have large effects.
- The arts teach students to think through and within a material.
- The arts help children learn to say what cannot be said.
- The arts enable us to have experience we can have from no other source and through such experience to discover the range and variety of what we are capable of feeling.
- The arts' position in the school curriculum symbolizes to the young what adults believe is important.

The instrumental arguments today against the arts such as the uncertainties of career prospects if students pursue the arts, and the need for "more important" subjects to take precedence, do not stack up

and blatantly miss the point. The arts are not just instrumental means to an end. They represent the innate human need to express deep feelings in ways that word and number cannot. They enhance and deepen our lives provoking feelings of curiosity, fascination, and insight. The ancient roots of the arts in our existence on earth underline the persistent and prevailing need for us to create and appreciate art. Arts education should provide a venue for students to express themselves.

We encountered wide agreement that one of the central purposes of arts education is to provide all learners with tools and opportunities to engage in and appreciate expressive experiences across the arts disciplines. Many people we spoke with stressed that the arts provide a unique opportunity for students to express themselves beyond verbal language. Elliot Eisner told us that it “has to do with the symbolic character of art, to be able to convey to others meanings that will not take the impress of literal language.” Speaking of the nature of musical experiences, writer and arts educator David Myers says, “What drives musicians as musicians? What we believe is that it’s that intrinsic, expressive phenomenon... We can’t get to it in words and kids need that kind of experience.”

It’s not simply about celebrating the release of emotion, but about “maximizing opportunities for young people to contribute and participate in their own expressive vernaculars and to link them to larger histories that they feel included in that perhaps have been excluded in the past.” Engaging in the arts allows students to represent and mold their own lives. Soep continues, “Nurturing expressive culture in its various forms is, should be, a crucial purpose within arts education... “The more that [the scope of expressive culture] shrinks and gets shut out of learning experiences... the fewer recourses [students] have to intervene in their own lives, impact on their communities, and feel like they are contributing in an active way as citizens in the world.” Expression is also important because it makes personal development possible by providing individual students with multiple ways to “be themselves” that they may not be able to access otherwise. In our interview, Bennett Reimer described how the expressive nature of the arts enables self-discovery: “You could say that in the arts you express yourself. Heck no. You’re finding yourself out! What you’re creating is yourself. You can create in one way and realize it’s not right and then do it differently.

Importance of Teaching and Learning through Arts:

Art-based learning aims to improve the student's cognitive (planning, remembering, and reflecting) as well as affective (social and emotional) and psychomotor (use of body and movement) abilities. Practical education in fine arts helps students to see what they look at, hear what they listen to, and feel what they touch. Through engagement in the fine arts, students can stretch their minds beyond the boundaries of the printed text or the rules of what can be proven. One of the principal aims in art education is to develop student confidence in their own ability to create art through experiential learning. This involves students working through creative processes, relating to the content as learners, but having to address both the process of their learning, and how this learning may impact their teaching of art. They record all of these in their art journal “an artistic process for recording personal insights with constructed images and personal reflections” (Evans-Palmer, 2018).

The need for individualization of the educational process demands creating flexible, alternative and dynamic teaching and learning strategies. Art expression in all of its variants offers a path to deep insight into and reflection on a range of content from different points of view, fostering integrative and multisensory experiences. In this way, the artistic experience accumulated through various modalities of transfer becomes a connection issue between different content and objectives, a support and point of departure in the design of didactic materials for different subjects, and a source of motivation to improve teaching and learning in other educational areas. However, this is based on the recognition that new media and digital technologies deal mostly with visual images of all kinds and their combination with other expressive instruments, as well as with auditory, kinaesthetic and verbal experiences, as an essential element in the interpretation and comprehension of data within different school subject areas. In most schools, their lack of innovative content contributors other matters, by the transmission of content in a way outdated. Therefore, the university should design a training plan that innovatively is able to train these future teachers about the educational potential of arts education.

In a globalized society, in which the image and visual culture are gaining increasing importance, it is necessary to the development of Arts Education to focus on learning goals through observation, as well as the great potential holds for cognitive development, expression, creativity and talent.

The faculty of arts education in the field should be acutely aware of this reality and to build new models that are enriching and motivating, feeling that it is relevant to oneself. The aim is to offer our students, future teachers of a much more extensive in the field of arts education, working identity as a source of knowledge and encouraging their creativity and talent so they can feel safe when imparting the subject of Art Education. If you think and generate ideas, are able to be creative and make use of their imagination to offer new activities and proposals to prospective students.

Conclusion:

Art making is risky. It is “like beginning a sentence before you know its ending” One of the vital elements in creativity is the ability to tolerate the feelings and struggles that come from bringing something new into being. Bayles and Orland argue that “uncertainty is the essential, inevitable and all-

pervasive companion to your desire to make art. And tolerance for uncertainty is the pre-requisite to succeeding” These important qualities are fostered when children are engaged in art-making. In many respects, children are better than adults at this and the last thing we as teachers should do is stifle their tolerance to the inevitable uncertainties inherent in the creative process.

Do the arts make us more creative? Yes, but only if they are taught well. An art lesson can be as tedious and prescriptive as a lesson in any subject area. Conversely, a lesson in mathematics or science can be highly creative and innovative. The role of the teacher is crucial in providing the opportunities for creative expression. What the arts do invite however is more license and more scope for pushing the boundaries of knowledge. The arts by their very nature kindle our creative urge and extend our creative capacities. When the drudgery and banality of life threatens to extinguish our dreams, the arts reawaken us to beauty and the endless possibilities that thrive in our imaginations. Moreover, the arts do not only provide pleasing aesthetics. They also provoke, challenge, stir, and confront. The arts help us to explore difficult issues in ways that enlighten and inform. Strong feelings, complex social and political issues, bigotry and prejudice can be examined through the arts. In such cases the arts raise consciousness and promote social justice.

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